

A “combi-encapsulant” for enhanced performance of glass-free lightweight crystalline silicon solar PV modules

F.Lisco¹, Alessandro Virtuani¹, Christophe Ballif^{1,2}

¹ École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Institute of Microengineering (IMT), Photovoltaics and Thin Film Electronics Laboratory (PV-Lab), Rue de la Maladière 71b, 2000 Neuchâtel, Switzerland

² CSEM, PV-center, Jaquet-Droz 1, 2000 Neuchâtel, Switzerland
Fabiana Lisco
fabiana.lisco@epfl.ch

Abstract— Lightweight crystalline silicon (c-Si) PV modules with a weight of 5kg/m², by substituting the typical front glass with a thin polymer sheet and the standard back sheet by a composite sandwich structure are presented here. With this work, we propose the use of a “combi-encapsulant”, as a front sheet for the proposed lightweight composite PV modules. With the final goal of manufacturing a lightweight structure able to withstand environmental and mechanical stress tests (following the IEC 61215 [3]), as combined sequential tests.

Keywords—lightweight PV modules, encapsulants, frontsheet, environmental and mechanical test.

I. INTRODUCTION

The possibility of producing a c-Si lightweight PV module with a weight of 5kg/m², by substituting the typical front glass with a thin polymer sheet and the standard back sheet by a composite sandwich structure, has been presented with our previous works [1,2]. These composite structures are usually composed of two skins bonded to a core, using a stiff adhesive. This represents a great advantage, especially for BIPV, VIPV applications, comparing to conventional solar photovoltaic (PV) modules, made with c-Si solar cells, which are typically glass/foil modules with a weight of 12-14 kg/m², or glass/glass modules weighting 14-20 kg/m² or even more (depending on the glass thickness). One of the main challenges to ensure reliability and long-term performance of these devices is to select the right BOM (bill of material) to build up the module stack. As well known, encapsulants represent a key part in the PV structure, acting as the bonding layer between the front or back sheet and the PV cell. Therefore, they need to provide excellent adhesion between these components, which is achieved via lamination. They also have to be transparent and provide outstanding electrical insulation and impact resistance to the module. All these properties must be retained after years of exposure to the UV from the sun or other severe weather conditions.

From our previous work, we found two optimal candidates for the frontsheet, a TPO and a POE [2], The aim of this work is to investigate the properties of a combination of these 2 encapsulants, which we will label “combi*-encapsulant” (*from combined), placed at the frontsheet of our LW PV stack. In

literature, there is not available resource that focuses on combining two different polymers; with this study, we want to show the advantages of using the “combi” instead of the single materials. We observed that, pairing the two materials, there was a synergistic interaction of their properties leading to improved stability of the PV stack towards severe stress conditions (mechanical and environmental). The so-called “combi-encapsulant”, is composed by a POE (polyolefin elastomer) and a TPO (thermoplastic olefin). The study will go through the degradation behavior of this combo-structure, upon exposure to two different accelerated- ageing tests (DH and ultraviolet (UV) irradiation), comparing it to the most widely used Ethylene Vinyl Acetate (EVA). The front sheet, as one of the main constituents of lightweight modules, has to provide high transparency, excellent electrical insulation and protection for the solar cells from airborne pollutants and moisture ingress. It is also of paramount importance in providing the required mechanical stability and protecting the solar cells from hail impacts, or impacts against other objects. EVA has dominated the PV industry as the encapsulant of choice; however, numerous studies from late 1990s until today, report that PV module performance reduces, also due to the degradation of the encapsulant. Browning/yellowing (which reduces the light reaching the solar cells), moisture absorption and acetic acid formation (which causes corrosion of metallization), delamination and bubble formation are the typical forms of EVA degradation. Even though degradation of polyethylene based polymers has been largely studied and reported in literature [4], more in detail studies regarding formulations for PV applications, are still in progress. Moreover, in literature there is no such a study about the use of a combined structure of TPO and POE encapsulants. This work would like to make a step forward and playing outside the mainstream: a TPO, a POE, both commercially available, and a “combi-encapsulant” (obtained combining the TPO and POE layers), will be investigated, by using UV-Vis spectrophotometry, rheology and mechanical analyses. Their properties will be compared to the most common EVA potant. The final goal is to show the advantages of using the combi-encapsulant, as a front-sheet of PV lightweight modules. Hail test, mechanical load and UV, DH tests will be also performed to investigate the reliability of the

module structure with the proposed combo-encapsulant. These modules will be then characterised electrically (to extract IV parameters) and by means of electroluminescence (EL) to visualize the induced damages.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

II.A OUR APPROACH

We already demonstrated the possibility to produce a lightweight PV module with a weight of 5kg/m^2 , by substituting the typical front glass with a thin polymer sheet and the standard backsheet by a composite sandwich structure [2]. An example of lightweight 16-cell module manufactured in our laboratory is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : A picture of a 16-cells LW module.

Our main goal is manufacturing a lightweight structure able to withstand DH, UV exposure and mechanical tests (following the IEC 61215 [3]), as combined sequential tests, such as hail test followed by DH and UV exposure.

II.A.1 Encapsulant preparation

Since providing high transparency is one of the main requirements for a front sheet material, optical analysis (T% and R% measurements) have been performed. To understand/simulate the behavior of these materials, before and after the lamination process (using the ETFE-polymer-ETFE configuration), optical measurements were carried out, both on the pristine investigated encapsulants and the ones subjected to lamination. Following the same configuration *ETFE-polymer-ETFE, the thermal and mechanical properties have been also studied.

II.A.2 Mini-modules production

One-cell ($156 \times 156 \text{ mm}^2$ Al-BSF c-Si solar cells with 5 busbars) mini-modules are produced according to Figure 2. The same backsheet (BS) structure was used in the manufacturing of all samples. The BS is made by glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) skins ($\sim 0.7 \text{ mm}$ thick), glued to a light honeycomb core (6 mm thick) with an elastomeric encapsulant. The lightweight PV modules structure contained an external $100 \mu\text{m}$ fluorine-based polymer (ETFE) layer, combi encapsulants (TPO-POE), c-Si solar cells and the BS sandwich structure.

Figure 2: A schematic diagram of the LW structure used for this work with the inclusion of the combi-encapsulants in the frontsheet

II.A.3 Encapsulants and PV modules characterizations

Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy is used to measure the optical properties (Transmittance, T, Reflectance, R) and the yellowness index (YI) of the investigated polymeric PV materials. The yellow index is a number that indicates the degree of deviation of a test sample from colorless (or white) towards yellow. The YI was measured according to the ASTM Standard C313-10 [5]. A UV-Vis-near-infrared spectrophotometer (Lambda 950 equipment from Perking Elmer), dual-beam, has been used, covering the spectral range from 250 to 2500 nm, with a measurement increment of 1 nm. The system is equipped with an integrating sphere to measure the total transmittance and reflectance [6].

Rheology is used to describe and assess the flow and deformation of materials under the effect of an applied force [8]. It is useful to understand the mechanical behaviour of materials as a function of stress, strain, temperature and pressure. An oscillatory deformation is applied to the encapsulant, their resulting response to stress-strain is time-dependent and their deformation partially reversible. With this work the storage modulus, G' (which is a measure of the elasticity of the materials), has been investigated to better understand and predict the viscoelastic behavior of the different encapsulants, once incorporated in the PV module stack. The measurements were performed by using an MDR 3000 Professional by Montech Werkstoffprüfmaschinen GmbH in a temperature range $50-170^\circ\text{C}$.

Tensile test was performed to measure the adhesion strength between the different encapsulants integrated in the PV stack. The Young modulus, or elastic modulus, E (expressing the encapsulants rigidity and the maximum stress which a material can withstand before failure), has been estimated. The test was performed using an Instron Zwick Roell Z020 mechanical testing instrument equipped with a 1kN load cell in a displacement control test at a fixed rate of 100 mm/min at room temperature.

The Hail test was performed according to IEC 61215-2:2016 [3].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.A Polymers characterization

Since providing high transparency is one of the main requirements for a front sheet material, optical analyses (T%, A% and R% measurements) have been performed. Figure 2 shows the EVA, TPO, POE and “combi-encapsulant” optical measurements, considering the polymers after seeing the same lamination process, as they would have experienced in the PV stack. To simulate the behaviour of these materials in the actual PV stack module, the lamination process (using the ETFE-polymer-ETFE configuration) was carried out. Usually, encapsulant materials show a UV cut-off wavelength, between 300 and 400 nm, below which the transmittance is lower than 10% [9]. As expected for a transparent material with a refractive index of ~1.5, [2], EVA transmits ~91% light, effectively from ~400 nm to ~1100 nm, as the POE, while the TPO transmits ~91% from the UV region to the entire visible spectrum. However, one of the two materials shows ~91 of transmittance, along the entire UV-vis spectrum, whilst the other ones present the UV cut-off, likely due to UV absorbers added in the formulation.

Figure 3: Transmittance (a) and Reflectance (b) measurements for TPO, POE, EVA and “combi-encapsulant” coupons, after the lamination process (ETFE-encapsulant-ETFE).

The highly transparency of these encapsulants, confirms these materials as good candidates to be used in the front sheet structure, and above all, the combined material presents optimal

optical properties. The samples were aged under damp heat (DH) test, up to 3000 hours, in a climate chamber WLK 100 from Weiss Umwelttechnik GmbH. The temperature was set at 85°C and relative humidity was set at 85%. Samples were withdrawn from the climate chamber after 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500 and 3000 hours of exposure. Then, characterized by UV-Vis analysis. To evaluate the effect of UV radiation, samples were aged in a UVTest™ Fluorescent UV Weathering instrument from Atlas Material Testing Technology LLC. The test cycles were programmed according to the standard IEC TS 62788-7-2:2016 [6], using fluorescent lamps with an irradiation peak at 340 nm and the maximum dose applied was 60 kW h/m² (as for the IEC61730:2016 [7]). Samples were withdrawn from the UV test after being exposed to a dose of 19 kW h/m², 38.5 kW h/m², 57.75 kW h/m² and 60 kW h/m², followed by optical characterization.

Figure 4: Transmittance and Reflectance measurements for each encapsulant, after the lamination process (ETFE-encapsulant-ETFE) along the DH exposure (a) and YI versus DH (b) and UV (c) exposure time for each encapsulant investigated.

After 3000 hrs of DH exposure, 2.2% loss in transmittance was observed for the TPO and 2% for POE while the combined-encapsulant showed only 1.1% loss (measured @500nm). Along the optical measurements, the YI (yellow index) was plotted, showing evident discoloration (yellowing appearance) for the EVA coupon, while the “combi-encapsulant” maintained these properties in between the TPO and POE, without dramatic changes, visually noticeable. Along the DH exposure, a decrease in transmittance values in the blue range of the spectra (380 nm–

500 nm) was observed for the coupons under investigation. A slight decrease of the UV cut-off values was observable, as well as an increase of the transmittance value in the region between 250 and 350 nm, which might be correlated to the consumption of the UV absorbers. Figure 4a) shows the “combi-encapsulant” behaviour during the DH exposure. A similar study has been carried out for the UV exposure, where interesting and different behaviour have been observed. No evident changes were detected up to 1000 hours of UV exposure, as shown in Figure 4c).

Rheology analysis is used to describe and assess the flow and deformation of materials under the effect of an applied force [8]. Figure 5 shows the logarithmic trend of the *storage or elastic modulus*, G' , (representing the material elasticity) and the *loss or viscous modulus* G'' , (representing, as the name suggests, the viscosity part), as a function of temperature, T . A comparison between the TPO, POE and combi-encaps is here reported. The storage modulus G' and loss modulus G'' showed that the combi-encaps has properties exactly in between the two materials, showing a viscoelastic behaviour, with $G'' > G'$, along the investigated temperature range. The TPO encapsulant is stiffer, in the temperature range from 50°C to 150°C, while the POE appears to be the softest encapsulant among the three, in the same T range (Figure 5). As the temperature increases, the $\lg G'$ modulus values decrease differently for the investigated polymers. Looking at the combi-encaps_ $\lg G'$, red curve in the graph, it remains perfectly in between the other 2 polymers. Softening points, corresponding to phase transitions of the material, are observed: at 60°C (because of the strong contribution of the POE), between 60 and 80°C (as a strong contribution of the TPO) and again between 90-130°C (as a contribution of both, TPO and POE). This analysis allows understanding how to process the new material, in particular during the lamination step. In addition, it confirmed that using a combi-encaps, pairing the two materials POE and TPO, there was a synergistic interaction of their properties, required for the front sheet of our stack.

Figure 5: Rheological measurements for the POE, TPO and combi-encapsulants, as received, with the $\lg G'$, $\lg G''$ represented as a function of Temperature.

With this work the storage modulus, G' (which is a measure of the elasticity of the materials), has been investigated to better understand and predict the viscoelastic behavior of the “combi-encapsulant”. The measurements were performed by using an MDR 3000 Professional by Montech GmbH in a temperature range 50-170°C. In addition, the Young Modulus was determined and compared with the other encapsulants, as reported in Table 1, showing the properties of the combi-coupon being in between the two materials, TPO and POE, as expected.

Table I: Young Modulus, calculated for the TPO, POE and “combi”.

	TPO	POE	Combi-encaps
Young Modulus (Gpa)	0.136	0.003	0.073

These results confirmed our choice of using the combi-encapsulants for the front-sheet from our previous study [2], it was understood the need of placing a rigid support at the back of the structure (behind the solar cells), while the front side needed to be a compromise, between the stiffer TPO and the softer POE. With the combination of the two materials, we could obtain the required properties.

As from our previous work [2], the adhesion between the TPO and POE layers was checked by performing the peeling test and the results showed a strong adhesion between the two layers (>40 N/cm).

III.B mini-module characterisation

Once deeply characterised the candidate combo material, we have prepared a series of mini LW PV modules using the *combi-encap* as frontsheet and exposed them to a sequence of accelerated aging tests, following IEC 61215-1:2016. Here, we present the results of a 1-cell LW mini module, subjected to sequential stress tests: Hail Test (chosen as pass-fail control test [2]), DH exposure (1000hrs) and UV exposure (30kWh/m²). The mini module perfectly passed the sequential tests as the EL and IV show, confirming that using this *combi-encaps* as a

frontsheet of the PV stack, allows it to withstand severe stress conditions, only reporting 0.3% loss in I_{sc} .

Figure 6: IV curves a) and electrical parameters b) of the 1-cell mini module before and after exposure to the sequence Hail Test, DH (1000hrs) and UV exposure (30kWh/m²).

Following the IEC 61215-1:2016, and part of the sequence C, a 1-cell mini module was subjected to the hail test (HT) followed by the UV exposure (30kWh/m²) and the Thermal Cycling (TC-216 cycles) test. The electrical performances as the EL images confirmed that the sequence of testing was successful.

Furthermore, following the IEC 61730, as part of the sequence B, a 1-cell mini module was subjected to 400 hours of DH (instead of 200 hours, as reported in the IEC standard), followed by 2000 hours of UVA exposure (which corresponds to 77kWh/m²).

Figure 7 (a,b) shows the electrical performances measured along the DH and UVA exposure (every 500 hours), in Figure c) the EL images after 400hrs DH and 2000hrs UVA exposure are reported.

Figure 7: IV curves and normalized electrical parameters of the 1-cell mini module before and after exposure to the sequence DH (400hrs) and UVA exposure (2000hrs_77kWh/m²)

The performances confirmed that the lightweight PV modules, with the optimised structure and the use of the combi-encaps in the frontsheet, successfully passed the sequence of accelerated stress tests. It is important to mention that the modules exposed to such described tests, were introduced in the chambers, intentionally, without any edge sealant, meaning that the modules were frameless, with no protection for the cells and the stack, in general. This implies that the performances could only improve with the perfectly sealed final structure. These results are currently in progress and will be presented in a follow up work.

The use of the single encapsulants, TPO and POE, has been also investigated, for comparison, in the LW PV stack. The respective configurations have been proposed: BS (backsheet)-solar cells-TPO-ETFE and BS-solar cells-POE-ETFE. The use of the single encapsulants in the PV stacks did not provide the same results obtained for the configuration with the combi-encaps.

Failures were observed after the hail test, when the only POE polymer is used as front sheet and power losses >5%, due to

degradation of the metallic interconnections, when the only TPO encapsulant is used as front sheet of the stack. Even after a sequence of stress tests (HT, DH, UV) the LW PV stack, with the inclusion of combi-encaps in the front sheet, showed a degradation <5%, assessing that the modules succeeded the standards tests, according to the IEC 61215.

IV CONCLUSIONS

The use of a “*combi-encapsulant*”, as a combination of TPO and POE polymers, is here proposed to be used for the front-sheet of LW PV modules. A complete study of the physical, optical, electrical, mechanical, thermal properties of this combo material has been presented. With this work, we investigated the advantage of using the *combi-encapsulant* instead of single polymers, to obtain the optimal frontsheet structure for our lightweight PV modules, providing a robust mechanical support to withstand severe stress conditions. Currently in literature, there are no studies about combined polymeric materials to be used in the LW PV stack. In this work, UV, DH and mechanical stress tests were performed on lightweight PV structures, with the combi-frontsheet encapsulant, to investigate their performance and durability. After each test, electrical, and morphological characterisations were performed, to finally assess the enhanced performances reached with the inclusion of the combi material in the stack. This study showed that the degradation of the LW PV stack, even after a set of sequential testing (HT, DH, UV), was <5%, assessing the robustness and resilience of the structure. These results confirmed also that the PV stack with this current configuration passed the stress tests, according to the IEC 61215. Our goal was to find a reliable, robust configuration, maintaining high optical transmittance and ideal thermo-mechanical properties, to withstand severe stressed conditions. This study was an important way to combine the peculiar properties of the single encapsulants, *tuning* them into this “combi” configuration. The use of the combi-encaps allowed not only to provide electrical and durable performances, but also to set the bases for a low-cost PV lightweight product, as for our planned next scaling-up step.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was funded by the European H2020 RE-COGNITION project (Grant Agreement ID: 815301). We acknowledge all PV-lab team members and particularly Xavier Niquille for his support with the experimental work and Leonardo Pires da Veiga (CSEM) for his help performing Rheological and DSC measurements.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. C. Martins, V. Chapuis, F. Sculati - Meillaud, A. Virtuani, and C. Ballif, “Light and durable: Composite structures for building - integrated photovoltaic modules,” *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, p. 12, 2018.
- [2] F. Lisco, A. Virtuani, C. Ballif, “Optimisation of the Frontsheet Encapsulant for Increased Resistance of Lightweight Glass-Free Solar PV Module”, 37th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, EUPVSEC, pp. 777 – 783, 2020.
- [3] IEC61215, “Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV)modules-Design qualification and type approval-Part2: Test procedures”, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2016.
- [4] Barretta, C.; Oreski, G.; Feldbacher, S.; Resch-Fauster, K.; Pantani, R. “Comparison of Degradation Behavior of Newly Developed Encapsulation Materials for Photovoltaic Applications under Different Artificial Ageing Tests”, *Polymers* 13, 271, 2021
- [5] D. Miller et al., "Examination of an Optical Transmittance Test for Photovoltaic Encapsulation Materials", SPIE Optics & Photonics 2013 San Diego, California August 25–29, 2013.
- [6] IEC TS 62788-7-2/ED1, “Measurement procedures for materials used in photovoltaic modules - Part 7-2: Environmental exposures - Accelerated weathering tests of polymeric materials” (IEC 82/1026/CD:2015).
- [7] IEC 61730-2:2016 “Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification – Part 2: Requirements for testing”, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2016.
- [8] J. Aho, “Rheological characterization of polymer melts in shear and extension: measurement reliability and data for practical processing,” PhD thesis, Tampere University of Technology, 2011
- [9] Cornelia, W., Hädrich Ingrid, K.W. “Overview of PV module encapsulation materials”. *Photovolt. Int.*, pp. 85–92, 2019.